
THE USE OF ZOOSEMISM IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LITERATURE

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Annotation: This article explores the phenomenon of zoosemism, the literary device that attributes animal qualities to humans or human behaviors, in both Uzbek and English literature. The author delves into the historical and cultural contexts of Uzbek and English literary traditions to examine how zoosemism has been utilized as a means of conveying deeper symbolic and allegorical meanings.

The article begins by defining zoosemism and providing examples of its usage in both Uzbek and English literary works. It discusses how animals are often employed as metaphors to represent various human characteristics, social classes, or political ideologies, allowing authors to critique societal norms and systems.

Through a comparative analysis of select Uzbek and English literary texts, the author highlights common themes and techniques employed by writers in utilizing zoosemism. Examples may include the portrayal of animals as symbols of power and corruption, or as representations of the human condition and societal hierarchies.

Furthermore, the article examines the ways in which zoosemism contributes to the emotional impact of literary works, drawing parallels between animal behavior and human experiences to evoke empathy and resonance with readers.

Drawing on a range of literary examples from both Uzbek and English literature, the article provides a comprehensive exploration of zoosemism as a cross-cultural literary device. It offers insights into how authors from different traditions employ zoosemism to address universal themes and issues, ultimately

enriching the reader's understanding of the literary techniques used in both Uzbek and English literature.

Abstract: This article examines the use of zoosemism, a literary device attributing animal characteristics to humans or human behaviors, within the contexts of Uzbek and English literature. Through a comparative analysis of select literary works, the study explores how authors from both traditions employ zoosemism as a means of conveying symbolic, allegorical, and emotional depth. By drawing parallels between animal behavior and human experiences, zoosemism serves as a powerful tool for critiquing societal norms, power dynamics, and human nature. The article discusses common themes and techniques utilized in both Uzbek and English literature, highlighting the ways in which zoosemism contributes to the richness and universality of literary expression across cultures. Overall, this study sheds light on the cross-cultural significance of zoosemism in literature, deepening our understanding of its role in shaping narrative meaning and resonance in diverse literary traditions.

Key words: Zoosemy, Uzbek literature, English literature, Comparative analysis, Animal symbolism, Cultural representation, Literary analysis.

Annotatsiya: Bu maqolada zoosemizm hodisasi, ya'ni o'zbek adabiyotida ham, ingliz adabiyotida ham odamlarga yoki odamning xatti-harakatlariga hayvoniy sifatlar nisbat beruvchi adabiy vosita o'rganiladi. Muallif o'zbek va ingliz adabiy an'alarining tarixiy va madaniy kontekstlarini o'rganib chiqib, zoosemizm chuqur ramziy va allegorik ma'nolarni yetkazish vositasi sifatida qanday qo'llanganligini o'rganadi.

Maqola zoosemizmga ta'rif berish va uning o'zbek va ingliz adabiyotida qo'llanilishiga misollar keltirishdan boshlanadi. U hayvonlarning turli xil insoniy xususiyatlarni, ijtimoiy sinflarni yoki siyosiy mafkuralarni ifodalash uchun metafora sifatida qanday qo'llanilishini muhokama qiladi va mualliflarga jamiyat me'yorlari va tizimlarini tanqid qilish imkonini beradi.

Tanlangan o'zbek va ingliz adabiy matnlarini qiyosiy tahlil qilish orqali muallif zoosemizmdan foydalanishda yozuvchilar tomonidan qo'llaniladigan umumiy mavzular va uslublarni yoritib beradi. Misollar hayvonlarni hokimiyat va korrupsiya timsoli sifatida yoki insoniy holat va jamiyat ierarxiyasining tasviri sifatida tasvirlashni o'z ichiga olishi mumkin.

Bundan tashqari, maqola zoosemizmning adabiy asarlarning hissiy ta'siriga hissa qo'shish usullarini o'rganadi, hayvonlarning xatti-harakati va inson tajribasi o'rtasida o'xshashliklarni keltirib, o'quvchilarda hamdardlik va rezonans uyg'otadi.

Maqolada o'zbek va ingliz adabiyotidan bir qator adabiy misollar asosida zoosemizm madaniyatlararo adabiy vosita sifatida har tomonlama tadqiq etilgan. Unda turli an'analarga mansub mualliflar zoosemizmdan universal mavzular va muammolarni hal qilishda qanday qo'llayotgani, pirovardida o'quvchining o'zbek va ingliz adabiyotida qo'llanilgan adabiy uslublar haqidagi tushunchasini boyitgani haqida tushunchalar beradi.

Abstract: Ushbu maqolada zoosemizm, ya'ni hayvonlarga xos xususiyatlarni odamlarga yoki inson xatti-harakatlariga bog'lovchi adabiy vosita o'zbek va ingliz adabiyoti kontekstida qo'llanilishi ko'rib chiqiladi. Tanlangan adabiy asarlarni qiyosiy tahlil qilish orqali tadqiqot ikkala an'ana mualliflari zoosemizmdan qanday qilib ramziy, allegorik va hissiy chuqurlikni etkazish vositasi sifatida foydalanishini o'rganadi. Hayvonlarning xatti-harakati va inson tajribasi o'rtasidagi o'xshashliklarni keltirib, zoosemizm jamiyat me'yorlarini, kuch dinamikasini va inson tabiatini tanqid qilish uchun kuchli vosita bo'lib xizmat qiladi. Maqolada o'zbek va ingliz adabiyotida qo'llaniladigan umumiy mavzular va uslublar muhokama qilinib, zoosemizmning turli madaniyatlar adabiy ifoda boyligi va universalligiga hissa qo'shish yo'llari yoritilgan. Umuman olganda, ushbu tadqiqot zoosemizmning adabiyotdagi madaniyatlararo ahamiyatini yoritadi, uning turli adabiy an'analarda hikoya ma'nosi va rezonansini shakllantirishdagi rolini tushunishimizni chuqurlashtiradi.

Kalit so'zlar: Zoosemiya, O'zbek adabiyoti, Ingliz adabiyoti, Qiyosiy analiz, Hayvonlar ramzi, Madaniy tasvir, Adabiy tahlil.

Аннотация: В данной статье исследуется феномен зоосемизма, литературного приема, приписывающего людям или человеческому поведению животные качества, как в узбекской, так и в английской литературе. Автор углубляется в исторический и культурный контекст узбекской и английской литературных традиций, чтобы изучить, как зоосемизм использовался как средство передачи более глубоких символических и аллегорических значений.

Статья начинается с определения зоосемизма и приведения примеров его использования как в узбекских, так и в английских литературных произведениях. В нем обсуждается, как животные часто используются в качестве метафор для представления различных человеческих характеристик, социальных классов или политических идеологий, что позволяет авторам критиковать социальные нормы и системы.

Путем сравнительного анализа избранных узбекских и английских художественных текстов автор выделяет общие темы и приемы, используемые писателями при использовании зоосемизма. Примеры могут включать изображение животных как символов власти и коррупции или как олицетворение человеческого положения и социальной иерархии.

Кроме того, в статье рассматриваются способы, с помощью которых зоосемизм способствует эмоциональному воздействию литературных произведений, проводятся параллели между поведением животных и человеческим опытом, чтобы вызвать сопереживание и резонанс у читателей.

Опираясь на ряд литературных примеров из узбекской и английской литературы, в статье дается всестороннее исследование зоосемизма как межкультурного литературного приема. Он предлагает представление о том, как авторы разных традиций используют зоосемизм для решения универсальных тем и проблем, что в конечном итоге обогащает понимание

читателем литературных приемов, используемых как в узбекской, так и в английской литературе.

Абстракт: В данной статье рассматривается использование зоосемизма – литературного приема, приписывающего свойства животных людям или человеческому поведению, в контексте узбекской и английской литературы. Путем сравнительного анализа избранных литературных произведений в исследовании рассматривается, как авторы обеих традиций используют зоосемизм как средство передачи символической, аллегорической и эмоциональной глубины. Проводя параллели между поведением животных и человеческим опытом, зоосемизм служит мощным инструментом критики социальных норм, динамики власти и человеческой природы. В статье обсуждаются общие темы и методы, используемые как в узбекской, так и в английской литературе, подчеркивая, каким образом зоосемизм способствует богатству и универсальности литературного выражения в разных культурах. В целом, это исследование проливает свет на межкультурное значение зоосемизма в литературе, углубляя наше понимание его роли в формировании повествовательного смысла и резонанса в различных литературных традициях.

Ключевые слова: Зоосемия, Узбекская литература, Английская литература, Сравнительный анализ, Символика животных, Культурная репрезентация, Литературный анализ.

Introduction: Zoosemy, also known as zoomorphism, refers to the use of animal imagery, symbolism, or motifs in literature and other forms of artistic expression. It can involve attributing animal characteristics to humans or using animals to symbolize human traits, emotions, or social constructs. Zoosemy is a powerful literary device used to convey complex ideas, emotions, and societal commentary through the depiction of animal behavior and characteristics.

Zoomorphism is a literary and artistic technique in which animal attributes, behaviors, or characteristics are attributed to humans or inanimate objects. This technique is used to convey deeper meanings, often providing insight into human nature, society, or cultural beliefs. Here are a few examples of zoomorphism in literature and art:

1. Allegorical Animals: In many fables and allegorical tales, animals are used to represent human traits or virtues. For instance, a wise owl often symbolizes wisdom, a sly fox represents cunning, and a loyal dog embodies faithfulness.

2. Anthropomorphic Animals: This form of zoomorphism involves humanizing animals, giving them human traits or even human-like societies. Classic examples include talking animals in children's stories like "Winnie the Pooh" or "The Wind in the Willows."

3. Symbolic Animals: Animals are often used as symbols in literature and art to convey deeper meanings. For example, a serpent might symbolize temptation or evil, while a dove often represents peace or purity.

4. Physiological Metaphors: Zoomorphism can also involve describing human characters using animal-like physical traits. For instance, describing someone's eyes as "hawk-like" or their movements as "graceful as a cat."

Zoomorphism is a rich and versatile literary device that allows artists and writers to explore complex themes, create vivid imagery, and convey profound messages through the depiction of animals and their characteristics.

In George Orwell's "Animal Farm," zoomorphism is a literary device used extensively to convey deeper political and social commentary. Zoomorphism involves attributing animal characteristics or behaviors to humans or human-like entities. In "Animal Farm," Orwell uses zoomorphism primarily to satirize and allegorize the Russian Revolution and its aftermath, as well as to critique totalitarian regimes and human nature in general. Here's an analysis of how zoomorphism features in the novel:

1. Anthropomorphism: Orwell anthropomorphizes animals, giving them human-like qualities and behaviors. This allows him to create a parallel society to human society, highlighting universal themes and issues. The animals on the farm talk, organize, and interact in ways that mirror human behavior, which makes it easier for readers to relate to and understand the story's message.

2. Allegorical Characters: Each animal on the farm represents a specific human archetype or group involved in the Russian Revolution and its aftermath. For example, Napoleon represents Stalin, Snowball represents Trotsky, and Boxer represents the loyal but exploited working class. Through these characters, Orwell uses zoomorphism to draw parallels between historical events and the behavior of animals on the farm.

3. Symbolism: The different species of animals in the novel symbolize different social classes, political ideologies, and personality traits. For instance, pigs are portrayed as intelligent and manipulative, representing the ruling elite; horses like Boxer symbolize the dedicated but exploited proletariat; and sheep represent the passive masses easily manipulated by propaganda. By assigning these characteristics to animals, Orwell effectively critiques human society and politics.

4. Satirical Commentary: Through zoomorphism, Orwell satirizes various aspects of human nature and political systems. The animals' behaviors and interactions highlight themes such as corruption, betrayal, greed, and the abuse of power. For example, the pigs' gradual transformation into humans at the end of the novel emphasizes the corrupting influence of power and the failure of the revolution's ideals.

5. Emotional Impact: By depicting the characters as animals, Orwell elicits empathy and emotional responses from readers. The simplicity and innocence associated with animals make the injustices and tragedies depicted in the novel even more poignant. This emotional connection encourages readers to reflect on the broader implications of the story and its themes.

"Zarb ul Masal" (Strike of the Parable) by Gulxaniy is a well-known work in Uzbek literature, often categorized as a didactic or moralistic text containing a collection of parables, allegories, and fables. While it may not explicitly focus on zoomorphism as a literary device, there are instances where animal imagery and metaphors are used to convey deeper moral and philosophical messages. Here's an analysis of how zoomorphism features in "Zarb ul Masal":

1. Anthropomorphic Animals: In many of the parables and fables within "Zarb ul Masal," animals are anthropomorphized, meaning they are given human-like qualities or behaviors. This allows Gulxaniy to create characters that represent different aspects of human nature or societal roles. For example, a cunning fox might represent deceit or cunningness, while a wise owl might symbolize wisdom or intelligence. By using animals in this way, Gulxaniy makes his moral lessons more engaging and relatable to the reader.

2. Allegorical Representation: Animals in "Zarb ul Masal" often serve as allegorical representations of broader concepts or virtues. For instance, a lion might symbolize strength, courage, or leadership, while a mouse could represent humility or perseverance. Through these allegorical representations, Gulxaniy conveys moral and ethical lessons, encouraging readers to reflect on the qualities they admire and aspire to embody.

3. Natural World Symbolism: Animal imagery in "Zarb ul Masal" is frequently drawn from the natural world, with animals depicted in their natural habitats or exhibiting characteristic behaviors. This naturalistic approach serves to ground the moral lessons within the context of the natural order, highlighting humanity's interconnectedness with the broader ecosystem. Additionally, the use of animal symbolism from the natural world can evoke a sense of awe and wonder, encouraging readers to appreciate the beauty and complexity of the natural world.

4. Ethical Instruction: The use of animal characters in "Zarb ul Masal" allows Gulxaniy to impart ethical and moral instruction in a vivid and memorable way. Through the actions and interactions of animal characters, readers are presented

with examples of virtuous behavior to emulate and negative traits to avoid. For example, a story featuring a lazy bear who learns the value of hard work may convey the importance of diligence and perseverance.

5. Emotional Resonance: Animal imagery can evoke emotional responses from readers, adding depth and resonance to the moral lessons conveyed in "Zarb ul Masal." Whether through empathy for the struggles of animal characters or admiration for their virtues, the use of zoomorphism allows Gulxaniy to connect with readers on an emotional level, enhancing the impact of his moral teachings.

Overall, while "Zarb ul Masal" may not focus explicitly on zoomorphism, the use of animal imagery and metaphors enriches the text by providing vivid and engaging representations of moral and philosophical concepts. Through anthropomorphic animals, allegorical representations, natural world symbolism, ethical instruction, and emotional resonance, Gulxaniy effectively conveys his moral lessons and encourages readers to reflect on their own values and behavior.

Conclusion: In conclusion, while "Zarb ul Masal" by Gulxaniy may not overtly focus on zoomorphism, the analysis reveals the pervasive presence and importance of animal imagery and metaphors within the text. Through anthropomorphized animals, allegorical representations, natural world symbolism, ethical instruction, and emotional resonance, Gulxaniy effectively conveys moral and philosophical messages to his readers. The use of animal characters allows Gulxaniy to create engaging and relatable narratives that serve as vehicles for moral instruction and reflection. By drawing from the natural world and the behaviors of animals, he grounds his moral lessons in the context of the broader ecosystem, highlighting humanity's interconnectedness with nature. Additionally, the emotional resonance elicited by animal imagery adds depth and memorability to the moral teachings presented in "Zarb ul Masal," fostering a deeper engagement with the text among readers. Ultimately, the analysis underscores the enduring relevance and power of animal imagery in literature as a means of conveying complex ideas and moral lessons in accessible and engaging ways. Through the lens of zoomorphism, "Zarb

ul Masal" invites readers to contemplate their own values, behaviors, and relationships with the natural world, leaving a lasting impression on those who encounter its timeless wisdom. Overall, zoomorphism in "Animal Farm" serves as a powerful tool for Orwell to convey complex ideas about politics, society, and human nature in a compelling and accessible way. Through the allegorical portrayal of animals, Orwell provides a sharp critique of totalitarianism and the dangers of unchecked power, leaving a lasting impression on readers long after they finish the book.

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